

DIELECTRICAL PROPERTIES OF ALUMINIUM DOPED YTTRIUM IRON GARNET

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Abstract:

In the present work Al doped Yttrium iron garnet with formula $Y_3Fe_{4.8}Al_{0.2}O_{12}$ have been prepared by sol-gel auto combustion technique and the results on dielectric properties were reported. The formation of single phase garnet structure was confirmed through X-ray diffraction technique. XRD pattern was recorded at room temperature in 2θ range of $20-80^\circ$. Using XRD data structural parameters were calculated and their values in accordance with that reported in the literature. The dielectric measurements as dielectric constant, dielectric loss and dielectric loss tangent were carried out using LCR-Q meter as a function of frequency. The observed behavior of the dielectric parameters is in good agreement with the reported data.

Key Words: Yttrium iron garnet, Sol-gel, Aluminum doping, XRD, dielectric properties

Introduction

Ferrites are the ferrimagnetic oxides as proposed by L. Neel [1]. It consist of mainly iron oxide and metal oxide. However, the proportion of iron oxide and metal oxide may vary and leads to different types of ferrites. By virtue of structure ferrites can be of three types namely spinel ferrite, garnets and hexagonal ferrite [2]. Spinel ferrite and garnet have the cubic structure but are differ in interstitial sites. Spinel ferrite have two interstitial sites namely tetrahedral (A) and octahedral [B]. Whereas, garnet have three interstitial sites namely dodecahedral {c}, tetrahedral (d) and octahedral [a] sites. Due to different interstitial sites garnet can accommodate variety of cations and thereby brings change in the electrical as well as magnetic properties. Garnets can be basically used for making permanent magnets. The garnets and their derived compounds are known as important class of materials due to their magnetic, magneto-optical, magneto-resistive, thermal, electrical, magnetic and mechanical properties such as ferri-magnetism, high thermal conductivity, high electrical resistivity, controllable saturation magnetization, etc. These properties lead them to employ into several applications such as electronic devices like phase shifters, circulators, oscillators for microwave frequencies, sensors, magneto-optic sensors, anode materials for batteries, catalysts, and magneto-optical devices [3-5]. Many methods have been used to prepare garnet material especially $Y_3Fe_5O_{12}$. The conventional way of synthesizing this material is by solid state reaction of oxide/carbonate powders and calcination at high temperature ($>1200^\circ C$) [6]. However, this method has some inherent disadvantages such as chemical in homogeneity, coarse particle size, introduction of impurities during ball milling etc. To overcome these problems, several techniques have been developed for preparations of fine garnet powders, including sol-gel auto-combustion process method [7], sol-gel method [8], co-precipitation method [9] and micro-emulsion method [10]. The properties of $Y_3Fe_5O_{12}$ particles are strongly affected by the composition and microstructure,

which are sensitive to the preparation methodology used in their synthesis. The dielectric properties of garnet are important from the point of view of their high frequency applications.

Experimental

The garnet having the chemical formula as $Y_3Fe_{4.8}Al_{0.2}O_{12}$ was synthesized by the sol-gel auto-combustion method. The AR grade reagents as: yttrium nitrate, ferric nitrate, aluminum nitrate, and citric acid were used for the synthesis. The prepared powders of pure and Al doped YIG have been sintered at $900^{\circ}C$ for 6h and used for further characterizations. The crystalline phase of sintered YIG nanoparticles was observed by using powder XRD with Cu $K\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda=1.540 \text{ \AA}$). The dielectric properties have been investigated using LCR-Q meter as a function of frequency. The dielectric parameters like dielectric constant, dielectric loss and dielectric loss tangent have obtained from dielectric data.

Results and Discussion

X-ray diffraction (XRD)

Figure 1 represents X-ray diffractograph of Al doped Yttrium iron garnet recorded at room temperature. The diffraction pattern were recorded in the 2θ range of 20° to 80° with scanning rate of 2° per minute using Cu- $K\alpha$ radiation of wavelength 1.5406 \AA . A close analysis of the XRD pattern reveals the formation of single phase cubic garnet structure. Similar XRD pattern is reported for pure yttrium iron garnet in the literature [11, 12].

Figure 1: Typical XRD pattern of pure yttrium iron garnet

Using XRD data various structural parameters were obtained. The unit cell dimensions are determined from the d-spacing of a line by making use of the cubic formula for inter-planer spacing. The values of lattice constant for pure and Al doped yttrium iron garnet is given in table 1. It is observed from this table that on doping Al lattice constant found to decrease. The decrease in lattice constant due Al doping is attributed to lower ionic

radii of Al^{3+} (0.51 Å) as compared to higher ionic radii of Fe^{3+} (0.64 Å) ions. Using the values of lattice constant and molecular weight, the X-ray density of the prepared samples were calculated and the values are reported in table 1. The crystallite size was obtained using Scherrer's formula [13] considering the highest intensity peak i.e. (420) of the XRD pattern. The value of crystallite size as obtained is given in table 1 which confirms the nanocrystalline nature of the prepared samples.

Table 1: Crystallite size, lattice constant and X-ray density of pure and Al doped yttrium iron garnet

Compound	Crystallite size (nm)	Lattice constant (Å)	X-ray density (gm/cm ³)
$\text{Y}_2\text{Fe}_5\text{O}_{12}$	24	12.371	5.17
$\text{Y}_2\text{Fe}_{4.8}\text{Al}_{0.2}\text{O}_{12}$	28	12.356	5.19

Dielectric properties

The dielectric measurements were carried out on disc shaped pellets (10mm dia, 3mm thickness) as a function of frequency by using two-probe method. The surface of pellet was polished with silver paste for good ohmic contact. The real ϵ' and imaginary ϵ'' parts of the dielectric constant and loss tangent $\tan\delta$ of $\text{Y}_3\text{Fe}_{4.8}\text{Al}_{0.2}\text{O}_{12}$ were computed according to Smith and Wijn [14]. The variation of the dielectric constant ϵ' and dielectric loss ϵ'' with respect to frequency at room temperature is shown in Fig 2. It can be observed from figures 2 that, dielectric constant (ϵ') and dielectric loss (ϵ'') both decreases with increase in frequency. It can also be observed that dielectric loss (ϵ'') decreases with increasing frequency much more rapidly than (ϵ').

This behaviour of dielectric constant is attributed by assuming that mechanism of polarization in ferrite is similar to that of conduction mechanism. Iwauchi [15] reported strong co-relation between the conduction mechanism and dielectric behaviour of the ferrites. Fig. 2 shows the variation of dielectric loss tangent with frequency at 300K for all the values of 'x'. It is observed from Fig. 4 that, the parameter $\tan\delta$ decreases exponentially with the increase of frequency. Similar variation was observed for indium doped yttrium iron garnet

Figure 2: a) ϵ' b) $\tan \delta$ of pure and Al doped yttrium iron garnet

Conclusion:

The samples of pure and Al doped yttrium iron garnet in nanocrystalline form has been successfully prepared by sol-gel auto combustion technique. The crystallite size obtained from Scherrer's formula is of the order of 24-28nm. The single phase cubic garnet structure of the prepared samples was confirmed through XRD analysis. The structural parameters like lattice constant and X-ray density found to be in good agreement to that reported in the literature. The dielectric constant, dielectric loss and dielectric loss tangent all decreases exponentially with increase in frequency.

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